

Formula of π

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Yuji Masuda

(y_masuda0208@yahoo.co.jp)

$$\pi = \frac{2}{x} + 2 \cdot \arctan \left(\frac{1}{\tan \left(\frac{1}{x} \right)} \right)$$

$$\left(\because x \geq \frac{1}{\pi} \right)$$